

MODEL PROBLEMS IN EPHAPTIC INTERACTION

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ABSTRACT. In this brief paper, the authors present a handful of model problems in axon-axon interaction.

Axons can interact with one another. This is being currently studied in the neuroscience community. In [1, 2], the authors proposed current-mediated coupling between axons which led to synchronization in their rhythms. Further, three-dimensional geometry was introduced to better model realistic tracts in [2, 3]. In the present paper, we take the model so developed, and based on it, present a few problems or examples which one should be able to tackle based on the understanding gained from the aforementioned references.

Problem 1. If three axons are inclined at θ_1 , θ_2 and θ_3 degrees with an inter-axonal configuration matrix W' , it is proposed to find the law of inward electric field at any given node of any axon.

Exercise 2. Hence (ibid.) the induced inward current at any given node of any axon.

Problem 3. By combination of the relevant nodally induced inward currents, it is proposed to find the new current balance law for the insulated tract.

Exercise 4. Hence (ibid.) for a semi-insulated tract.

Problem 5. Using the new current balance law it is proposed to rederive the ephaptic propagation equation for the tract.

Exercise 6. And, to perform relevant simulations.

Problem 7. It is proposed to use mathematical induction or a direct derivation to find the current balance law for a general N number of axons.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aman Chawla. *On Axon-Axon Interaction via Currents and Fields*. PhD thesis, University of South Florida, 2017.
- [2] Aman Chawla, Salvatore Morgera, and Arthur Snider. On axon interaction and its role in neurological networks. *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Computational Biology and Bioinformatics*, 2019.
- [3] Aman Chawla, Salvatore D. Morgera, and Arthur D. Snider. Fields, geometry, and their impact on axon interaction. *Journal of Applied Mathematics and Physics*, 9(4):751–778, 2021.